

Web-based Resource Centre

Technical Guide

Horizon 2020

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Foreword

The Web-based Resource Centre is an online inventory providing functionalities for the collection, organization and retrieval of knowledge related to cultural tourism development. It provides information for scientists, policy-makers, stakeholders, NGOs, practitioners; data and maps related to the impact of cultural tourism in the case study areas; presentation of research results; policy recommendations/strategies; examples of good practices and the interpretative model for stakeholders` use.

Through this User`s Guide, you will get to know the main modules of the Resource Centre and its internal logic. The Guide will be revised in order to reflect the expanding functionalities of each available version.

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1. Entering the Web-Interface

The Resource Centre is accessible directly from the SPOT homepage through the menu point Resource Centre (as shown on Figure 1). It is accessible via computer and mobile phone as well.

1. Figure: Illustration of the layout of the Resource Centre

This online knowledge hub aims to function as a repository of information and links for scientific and practical purposes as well. It consists of seven menu points: the SPOT-IT Tool, Case study areas, Good practices, Services, External sources, Results and Contact Us. For those that seek to acquire more knowledge on cultural tourism in general and in the case study areas, the collection under 'External sources' and the case study area map found under 'Case study areas' serve as a junction point to information. The searchable list of SPOT research results under 'Results' serves to deepen knowledge on cultural tourism in the case study areas.

The support activities of SPOT under the 'Services' menu point provide stakeholders, investors, researchers, government and municipal officials information on opportunities related to the development of cultural tourism and support in the quality implementation of cultural tourism development projects. These activities can take different formats, such as policy recommendations, guidance on project implementation from formulation to monitoring. For those that seek to improve the success of cultural tourism development projects, the collection of good practices and policy recommendations helps to gain insight into successful cultural tourism policies and development programs.

The SPOT-IT tool as part of the Web-based Resource Centre is a GIS-based tool that provides decision support mechanisms for the development of cultural heritage attractions/sites in deprived remote and peripheral areas interested in establishing new, or developing existing cultural tourism sites to strengthen economic and social sustainability. The tool also seeks to indicate areas of additional development or improved sustainability in several urban areas that have historically suffered from over-tourism.

2. The SPOT-IT tool

The tool within the Web-based Resource Centre will help to facilitate the access of entrepreneurs, stakeholders, tourists and researchers to information and issues concerning the development of cultural tourism. This will advance the formulation and implementation of relevant policies and practices in Europe. SPOTIT Tool can simply be a flagship resource element in the database and the use of relevant data in decision-making.

The pilot version will be available in late 2021, its outputs will include scoring and rankings of geographical pixels based on their suitability for cultural tourism development and forecasts regarding the expected annual number of visitors of a suggested cultural tourism venture. It will also have a feature that allows local, cultural tourism and bottom-up initiatives to materialize via public participation platforms.

Currently the menu point contains a presentation introducing its functionality.

2. Figure: The layout of menu point 'The SPOT-IT tool'

3. The Case study areas

The consortium of SPOT is composed of 15 partners from 14 European countries and Israel. The 15 case study areas with varying levels of tourism flow bring in a wide range of knowledge about cultural tourism and its different types throughout Europe and Israel. The ‘Case study areas’ menu point contains an interactive map which users can click on to find out more about the case study areas. By clicking on a case study area users are provided with a short description about the tourism characteristics of the area and the purpose of researching that specific territory.

3. Figure: The layout of the menu point 'Case study areas'

4. External sources

For an extensive knowledge about the field, the catalogued collection of external resources provides a comprehensive list of organisations, reports and projects related to cultural tourism in one convenient place. Under the point ‘External sources’, users can find an inventory of external links, currently divided by five themes:

- Sources found under ‘Global organisations’ provide links to the websites of global organisations that are also involved in cultural tourism
- Sources found under ‘European organisations’ focus only on tourism organisations in Europe
- Sources found under ‘Reports and Perspectives’ are reports produced by European and world organisations focusing on cultural tourism
- Sources found under ‘COVID-19 Impact and Responses’ are reports produced by European and world focusing specifically on the impacts of COVID-19 on cultural tourism and the responses in tourism sector.
- Sources found under ‘Similar projects’ are links to the websites not just to our networking partners but to other projects with similar themes.

4. Figure: The layout of the menu point 'External sources'

5. Results

Under the point 'Results' (Figure 5) users can browse project related articles by keywords or can directly access them through clicking on the files listed below the keywords.

5. Figure: Layout of the menu point 'Results'

6. Contact Us

Under the point 'Contact Us' users have the opportunity to contact specific partners through the webmaster (Figure 6).

6. Figure: Layout of the menu point 'Contact Us'

7. Menu points under development

The library of 'Good practices' from our case study areas is intended to provide guidance for those that seek to improve the success of cultural tourism development projects. From good practices on cooperation to sustainable development of cultural tourism, users can explore best practices and gain insight into successful cultural tourism development programs.

The support activities of SPOT under 'Services' provide stakeholders, investors, researchers, government and municipal officials information on opportunities related to the development of cultural tourism and support in quality implementation of cultural tourism development projects. These activities can take different formats, such as policy recommendations, guidance on project implementation from formulation to monitoring.

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